

Comparison of Burnup Credit Loading Curve Methodologies for a Simplified Case with PWR Fuel: introduction to OECD/NEA/NSC/WPNCS SG13 study

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ABSTRACT

Existing Criticality Safety Evaluation (CSE) methodologies exhibit varying levels of conservatism and comprehensiveness, depending on the national regulations and application types. Some methodologies are based on "generic" Nuclear Criticality Safety (NCS) criteria, while others employ "case specific" ones. Case specific criteria may involve an adjusted calculation bias and an associated uncertainty for an application system k_{eff} . Alternatively, CSE methodologies may allow adjustments of nuclear data based on validation results. Different methodologies may be based on different approaches to interpret the validation results obtained for appropriate experimental benchmarks: either frequentist or Bayesian statistics, or a combination of both. Obviously, the optimal level of methodological complexity remains an open question, particularly in the context of big-scale industrial applications, such as NCS for used nuclear fuel. The impact of potential methodological differences on the engineering and safety requirements and associated economical metrics, e.g. for designing final disposal canisters and geological repository facility, is not immediately apparent. Specifically, the concept of 'loading curves' (LC) requires determination of minimal burnup versus initial fuel assemblies' enrichment to meet the NCS criteria. Making the LC practically efficient may require costly optimizations of the engineering solutions. To shed light on the variability of the NCS approaches, the WPNCS SG13 exercise on derivation of burnup credit LC for a simplified case with pressurized water reactor (PWR) fuel was launched at OECD/NEA/NSC.

Keywords. Criticality Safety, Burnup Credit, Loading Curves, Used Nuclear Fuel, SG13 Exercise

1. INTRODUCTION

This paper provides a brief summary on the preliminary results obtained within the OECD/NEA/NSC Working Party on Nuclear Criticality Safety (WPNCs) Subgroup 13 (SG13) exercise "Comparison of Burnup Credit Loading Curve Methodologies for a Simplified Case with PWR Fuel" [1], launched in December 2022. The SG13 study is a first of its kind assessment of the variability of the so called "loading curves" as a result of differences in methodologies and derivation criteria selected by participants [2],[3]. The work on the compilation of the SG13 results is still ongoing and will be published in the form of the NEA technical report [4].

The loading curve concept is a well-established option within the burnup credit (BUC) approach in the domain of NCS. A loading curve defines the minimum burnup required for the NCS reasons for a configuration of irradiated nuclear fuel, such as used fuel assemblies, e.g., as a function of an initial ^{235}U enrichment. It is a relevant approach, e.g. for transport/storage casks and repository/disposal canisters. However, there is significant variability in NCS methodologies worldwide, including the safety criteria. Specific NCS implementation options may differ in practice, depending on the national regulations, safety license applicant's methodology and/or its validation basis. There are no commonly followed recipes on how exactly loading curves should be derived. To partially investigate such topics, the SG13 exercise was initiated. The SG13 exercise focused on comparing existing NCS criteria that could be employed for deriving simplified loading curves by different institutions and in different countries. Conducting this study as an international exercise under the auspices of the NEA WPNCs [5] provided an opportunity to collect solutions from NEA member countries and various organizations, including nuclear regulators, industrial entities, research institutions and technical safety organizations. It should be noted, however, that the NCS criteria employed for the SG13 exercise are not fully realistic, as they may be missing essential components. Therefore, the SG13 findings may only partially illustrate the potential practical variability of the loading curves, and may require verification using more realistic pseudo-application models and constraints.

2. SG13 EXERCISE DESCRIPTION

2.1. Objective

The objective of the SG13 exercise was to facilitate a direct comparison of existing NCS approaches, which could be applied in practice, e.g., for analysis of disposal canisters loaded with UNF, but using a well-defined and simplified pseudo application case. For that, calculational needs and potential sources of participants' implementation variability were to be minimized as much as possible. Additionally, one of the most commonly used fuel types was selected for analysis. The study was therefore limited to:

- A 3D quarter symmetry sector model representing four identical PWR fuel assemblies (FAs) immersed in water and surrounded by a water reflector;
- A 17×17 UO_2 FA model, with uniform and predefined fuel composition;
- An arbitrarily selected and limited number of initial enrichments for fresh FAs;
- A fixed set of credited actinides and fission products, as used in previous WPNCs studies [6];
- A limited, fixed set of ICSBEP [7] benchmarks offered for the methodology validation step.

Note that in general, and in particularly the selected ICSBEP benchmarks do not include minor actinide nuclides and fission products. In reality, the lack of benchmarks or other measurements to validate nuclear data for fission products and minor actinide nuclides may require specific considerations. However, for the purposes of this exercise, this issue was not specially addressed. The benchmark specifications did not include a task related to defining an allowance for missing benchmarks for minor actinide nuclides and fission products. Nevertheless, given the practical importance of this issue for real-world applications, some participants opted to optionally account for the impact of missing validation. Similarly, the assumption of normality for the validation calculated-to-experimental (C/E) results was deemed adequate for the SG13 exercise. Thus, no need was assumed for applying additional margins due to the small C/E sample size, as the limited benchmark set was intended primarily to illustrate the principles of the participants' validation approaches, while keeping the calculation efforts minimized.

Thus, it should be stressed that this is a simplified exercise dealing with only limited parts of realistic CSE and BUC applications. Depletion calculations were excluded from the exercise and UNF compositions as a function of burnup, assuming zero decay time, were provided in the specifications. Uncertainties related to depletion calculations were not considered. Calculation biases and their uncertainties were to be determined based on the specified experimental benchmarks, optionally complemented by estimated k_{eff} uncertainties due to the nuclear data covariances. Participants were encouraged to use the same nuclear data source (ENDF/B-VII.1) when possible, to eliminate unnecessary sources of uncertainty in the results comparison.

The participants' task was to determine the BU values at which the model k_{eff} meets the NCS criteria for each initial enrichment, following their own methodologies. The exercise consisted of two parts: 1) a verification step, using a predefined USL of 0.95 (i.e., neglecting bias and uncertainty in the criticality calculations and considering only the "administrative margin" of 0.05), and 2) an application step, based on USLs determined by the participants themselves (taking into account participants' validation studies using the recommended ten criticality benchmarks).

2.1.1. Specifications

The pseudo application case proposed for the analysis consists of an arrangement of 4 FAs immersed in water, as illustrated in Figure 1. The distance of the FAs to each other (separation between the FA lattice surfaces) was set to 4 cm. A PWR FA design with a 17 x 17 pin layout and UO₂ fuel is assumed. The FA geometry is largely adopted from the Burn-Up Credit Criticality Safety Benchmark Phase VII [6]. For simplicity, fictitious fuel compositions corresponding to initial enrichments of 2.0 wt.%, 3.0 wt.%, 4.0 wt.% and 5.0 wt.% ²³⁵U and burnup values of 0 MWd/kg, 0.1 MWd/kg, 10 MWd/kg, 20 MWd/kg, 30 MWd/kg, 40 MWd/kg, 50 MWd/kg, 60 MWd/kg and 70 MWd/kg were considered. An axially and radially uniform burnup is assumed in the criticality calculations, i.e. only one specific fuel composition is present in all the pins of the 4 FAs at a time.

Figure 1. Pseudo-application case [3].

The list of the ten ICSBEP validation benchmark cases which were proposed to be used for USL determination included: LEU-COMP-THERM-006-001, LEU-COMP-THERM-007-001, LEU-COMP-THERM-011-001, LEU-COMP-THERM-014-001, LEU-COMP-THERM-039-001, LEU-COMP-THERM-062-001, MIX-COMP-THERM-001-002, MIX-COMP-THERM-002-002, MIX-COMP-THERM-003-006, MIX-COMP-THERM-004-001 [7].

3. RESULTS

3.1.1. Verification part

The first part of SG13 exercise included comparison of participants' k_{eff} results for the pseudo application case, without any adjustments, ND-related uncertainty estimates for the pseudo application case k_{eff} result, and LC results provided by the participants for the case of predefined USL=0.95. Using the predefined USL of 0.95 assumes that the bias and its uncertainty in the criticality calculations are neglected, and only the "administrative margin" is considered. The comparison of the resulting loading curves serves as a verification step to ensure that participants' criticality calculations for the specified models are performed correctly. Figure 2 presents the LC results provided by the participants for the case of predefined USL=0.95.

Figure 2. Case of "USL=0.95": Participants' LCs and the sample standard deviation [4].

3.1.2. Preliminary main results

The main part of the exercise consisted in comparison of the loading curves obtained with USL values determined by the participants themselves. In this case, participants' validation studies, using the recommended ten criticality benchmarks, were taken into account. The comparison of the resulting loading curves illustrates the level of agreement between different methodologies and associated NCS criteria that could be used for practical applications. Particularly, the methodologies applied by the participants can be basically attributed to two distinct groups: one based on the frequentist statistical approach and another - based on the Bayesian approach. The frequentist solutions outnumbered the Bayesian ones, but not by a large margin.

Figure 3 provides the major evaluation results for the solutions obtained with the ENDF/B-VII.1 library: the standard deviation and the maximum difference between the participants' loading curve results.

Figure 3. Standard deviation and spread of the results corresponding to "Participants USL, obtained with ENDF/B-VII.1" [4].

Next, based on the collected contributions, it is possible to assess the average difference between the loading curves produced with the criteria USL=0.95 and with participants' individual USL values (i.e. the difference between the average participants' loading curves obtained for the two USL options). This difference can be considered as the mean BU margin which is introduced based on the participants validation results, and it is demonstrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Difference between the loading curves produced with the criteria USL=0.95 and with participants' individual USL.

It should be noted that among the 21 collected results one contribution was obtained with an administrative margin different from 5 %, to be in line with participant's national regulations. Furthermore, another solution also stands out from the rest of contributions, since it was obtained with accounting for additional arbitrary safety margin to compensate the lack of validation support for MA and FP and the margin was conservatively assessed based on an engineering judgement.

While keeping the two mentioned contributions is valuable in the sense of showing how the loading curves variation can be sensitive to addition of most and least conservative extreme solutions, it is also reasonable to provide the results evaluation limited to the solutions obtained for the same conditions. Figure 5 shows the accordingly updated standard deviation value and the spread of the results.

Figure 5. Standard deviation and spread of results of the results corresponding to "Participants USL, obtained with ENDF/B-VII.1", excluding arbitrary postulated NDUQ; adm. margin = 5000 pcm [4].

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This paper provides a preliminary evaluation of the OECD/NEA/NSC WPNCs Subgroup 13 results. The SG13 study concerns a comparison of BUC loading curves obtained with different methodologies applied by participants, selected at their discretion, for a simplified model that, nevertheless, represents a realistic system to a significant extent.

The purpose of this study was not to qualify the applied methodologies but to assess the level of agreement between different methodologies, especially when NCS criteria are also selected by participants, as can be expected in practice. Clearly, different methodologies may exhibit varying levels of sophistication or conservatism. The solutions provided may also differ in accuracy or precision. However, the submitted solutions represent what participants consider the most appropriate for the given exercise. For this reason, all solutions that comply with the provided specifications are basically treated equally in the final statistical evaluation. There were however a couple of solutions which differed from the others to a significant extent. In order to present the obtained results in full detail, both cases of the collected data processing were employed: at first - for all results, and at second - excluding the most extreme solutions, conceptually deviating from the rest of the results.

It should be noted that this exercise is not directly representative of any practical licensing application for regulatory approval. Compared to realistic BUC assessments, the exercise does not account for depletion biases and uncertainties in the determination of the used fuel nuclide inventories. Temperature variations and abnormal conditions are not considered.

The goal of this exercise, however, was not to demonstrate a real-life BUC application but to compare the performance of different methodologies using a simplified model and well-defined constraints, such as a preselected set of validation benchmarks, without any advanced assessment of their applicability.

Based on the evaluated results, the following preliminary conclusions can be drawn:

- A reasonably good agreement is observed for LC with “USL = 0.95”.
- Larger differences are observed for LC with participant specific USLs.
- Bayesian model-based methodologies/NCS criteria provide the less penalizing results compared with the frequentist-based methodologies, which is found to be in line with recent independent studies with a different pseudo application case and validation basis [8].
- The additional BU required to meet applicants' specific reduced USLs varies from ~1.0 MWd/kg at 2wt.% enrichment up to ~1.5 MWd/kg at 5wt.% enrichment.

As the main outcome, SG13 study demonstrated that even when using the simplified model with consistent constraints and data sources, but different methods and NCS criteria, the spread of the obtained loading curves is quite noticeable. In fact, the differences in methodologies and NCS criteria appear to have a stronger impact than the effect of nuclear data uncertainties, which usually are the major source of criticality calculation uncertainties. However, participants' solutions can be grouped by main methodological or NCS criteria features, such as Bayesian and Frequentist statistics. Grouping solutions by methodology would significantly reduce variance. At the same time, it should be clarified that there is no reference method or solution for this exercise.

For real application cases, the sources of discrepancies between solutions would likely increase substantially (e.g., due to depletion calculations, axial or pin-wise burned fuel composition distributions, etc.). Another source of variation in real life applications would be the choice of validation benchmarks, which were prespecified and limited in number for this exercise. Since the SG13 study was done using quite simplified models and conditions, it can be recommended to continue the verification of BUC methods with more realistic pseudo application models and more practical constraints.

The work on the SG13 results compilation and analysis is still in progress and will be officially reported in the NEA publication [4]. In addition to participants' reference results evaluation, the NEA report will also present in detail participants' methodologies applied for the analysis, results of performed verification steps, as well as complementary sensitivity and test studies performed with modified NCS criteria or CSE methodologies, or different nuclear data libraries.

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